

NANOCOMPOSITE SCAFFOLDS BASED ON BACTERIAL CELLULOSE AND POLYLACTIDE TOWARDS THE 3D CULTURE OF HAEMOPOIETIC STEM CELLS

J J Blaker^{1,2}, K-Y Lee^{1,2}, A Mantalaris², A Bismarck^{1,2}

¹Polymer and Composite Engineering (PaCE) Group

²Department of Chemical Engineering and Chemical Technology

Imperial College London

South Kensington Campus

SW7 2AZ

Email: j.blaker@imperial.ac.uk

SUMMARY

Novel composite scaffolds have been fabricated using bacterial cellulose and polylactide using a combined ice microsphere templating and thermally induced phase separation route. The technique was developed to achieve both controlled interconnected pore structures and most importantly to result in pores lined with bacterial cellulose nanofibrils.

Keywords: Biomedical, Nanocomposite, Bacterial Cellulose, Tissue Engineering, Scaffold

INTRODUCTION

Haematopoietic stem cell cultures have generated intense interest due to their potential applications in cell-based therapies [1]. Haematopoietic stem cells generate the various blood lineages through successive series of intermediate progenitors, including common lymphoid progenitors and common myeloid progenitors. The common lymphoid progenitors generate B and T lymphocytes, and Natural Killer cells, while the common myeloid progenitors give rise to red cells, platelets, granulocytes, and monocytes. Further downstream of the myeloid and lymphoid stem cells are more mature progenitors that are restricted in the number and the type of lineages they can generate. Ultimately, terminally differentiated cells are produced that can neither divide nor undergo apoptosis after a period of time, which ranges from hours (for neutrophils) to decades (for some lymphocytes) [2]. These processes are regulated by the haematopoietic inductive microenvironment; a 3D structural and chemical microenvironment that regulates, through positive and negative signals, the survival, proliferation, and differentiation of haematopoietic stem cells [2,3]. Abnormalities in the regulation of haematopoiesis may lead to the development of bone marrow disorders, such as leukaemia. Treatment for such diseases is limited and can often only be cured by bone marrow transplant. The limited availability of suitable bone marrow

donors necessitates the development of haematopoietic cell expansion systems. Efforts have been made towards the reconstruction of *ex vivo* haematopoietic stem cell culture systems, which could have several potential clinical applications, especially in expansion of haematopoietic stem and progenitor cells for use in bone marrow transplantation [4]. The concept of cultivating haematopoietic cells along with stromal cells in two-dimensional (2D) flask cultures was suggested by Dexter in the late 1970s [5]. Although experimental work on culture dishes and flasks has provided invaluable information, there are important limitations in 2D systems, which ultimately result in the lack of long-term culture maintenance and multi-lineage differentiation. These limitations include the inability to provide a controlled culture environment, which can be overcome through the use of bioreactors. An important feature of the bone marrow's haematopoietic inductive environment is its 3D organisation, which is required in controlling *in vivo* the haematopoietic process. Consequently, the utilisation of support matrices that afford cells a 3D growth environment by enhancing cell-cell contact, promoting the spatial arrangement of cells, and supporting a high cell density due to their high surface area to volume ratio, has been explored [6-10]. Static 3D culture systems are disadvantageous due to nutrient diffusion limitations, which can be overcome, potentially, by the use of dynamic flow bioreactors [4]. Scaffold parameters such as porosity, interconnectivity and pore size are important characteristics for cell attachment, growth, and mass transfer [4,6,11]. Generally, these cells are difficult to culture in three dimensions and the current technology is confined to low volume two-dimensional growth. Expensive and complex growth factors must also be added to the cell culture media.

Bacterial cellulose fibrils are in the nanometer scale and are microscopically similar to collagen fibres, making them interesting to use as a collagen-mimicking component in scaffolds [12,13]. The non-woven ribbon of bacterial cellulose resembles the structure of native extra cellular matrices [12]. The future prospects of microbial cellulose in biomedical applications have been reviewed in detail elsewhere [12]. Bacterial cellulose has already found application in wound closure and healing [14], drug delivery, vascular grafting [15,16] and as a scaffold material for *in vivo* or *in vitro* tissue engineering [13]. Efforts have been made into controlling pore sizes and interconnectivity by cultivating a cellulose producing bacteria, *Acetobacter xylinum*, in the presence of a scaffold of paraffin wax and starch particles of various sizes [13]. Bacterial cellulose scaffolds of different morphologies and interconnectivity were prepared [13]. Bacterial cellulose has other attractive qualities as a filler in nanocomposite scaffolds; the cellulose fibrils impart a nanometer scale topology (they have diameters between 10 nm to 100 nm); they have a highly organised hierarchical structure resulting in high crystallinity (~90%); with a measured Young's modulus of about 114 GPa, which is comparable to that of glass fibres [17].

In this work we have developed a technique to provide controllable pores with interconnectivity in the range suggested by previous research [4], at the same time allowing the surface of the pore walls to be lined with cellulose nano-fibrils. Bacterial cellulose also acts to induce a more hydrophilic character to the relatively hydrophobic PLA and to improve mechanical properties (toughness and handling); the many hydroxyl groups on the surface of bacterial cellulose are available for functionalisation, protein adsorption and may act to promote cell attachment. We describe a technique to

combine bacterial cellulose with polylactide and produce scaffolds using the thermally induced phase separation route, which is built upon by combining with an ice-microsphere templating technique [18]. The thermally induced phase separation (TIPS) technique allows for the incorporation of bioactive and reinforcement phases into highly porous scaffolds with controlled porosity [19]. Composite porous microspheres have also been produced using the technique [20].

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Materials

Bacterial cellulose was extracted from a commercially available product, *Nata-de-Coco* (CHAOKOH[®] coconut gel in syrup Thep. Padung Porn Coconut Co. Ltd, Bangkok, Thailand). Dimethyl carbonate ($\geq 99.0\%$ purity), chloroform ($\geq 99.8\%$ purity), methanol ($\geq 99.8\%$ purity) and acetone ($\geq 99.8\%$ purity) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All reagents were used as received without further purification. Poly(D,L-Lactide) (PDLLA) with an inherent viscosity of 1.62 dl g^{-1} was purchased from Purac Biochem (The Netherlands).

Extraction and purification of bacterial cellulose from *nata-de-coco*

The coconut gels from *Nata-de-Coco* were rinsed three times with dH_2O to remove the sugar syrup. It was then blended using a variable speed laboratory blender (Waring Laboratory, Essex, UK) operated at maximum speed and homogenised (Polytron PT 10-35 GT, Kinematica.CH, Switzerland). The resulting blend of bacterial cellulose and sugar were purified by boiling a concentration of 0.6 (w/v %) in 0.1M NaOH at 80°C for 2 h to remove any remaining microorganisms and soluble polysaccharides [4]. Bacterial cellulose was recovered by successively centrifuged (15,000G for 15 min), homogenised and rinsed to neutral pH.

Hydrolysis of bacterial cellulose

Hydrolysis was performed in an effort to remove the amorphous regions and to reduce the length of the nano-fibrils [21,22]. Such action will diminish their tendency to form web-like structures and agglomerates. Bacterial cellulose was boiled under reflux at 125°C for 2 h in 2.5N sulphuric acid. The concentration of bacterial cellulose in the solution was 0.68 wt% as this is a concentration at which the solution is known to be stirrable. The reaction vessel was then quenched in ice-cold water and the hydrolysed bacterial cellulose was then successively centrifuged and homogenised to neutral pH. Finally, the cellulose was suspended in dH_2O at a concentration of 4 mg ml^{-1} . The suspension was poured into large Petri dishes covered with perforated foil and frozen in liquid nitrogen for 2 h. It was then subsequently freeze-dried (using a Modulyo freeze dryer, Edwards, UK) for 72 h.

Preparation of ice microspheres as *in situ* porosifiers

Ice microspheres were made using a facile procedure; freezing water mist generated from an ultrasonic fogger (Maplin electronics, UK). The ultrasonic fogger was placed in a water reservoir (depicted in Figure 1) and the water mist was blown into a sink of liquid nitrogen whereupon ice microspheres were formed. These microspheres were then sieved in liquid nitrogen to diameters ranging between 100-500 μm to yield a pore size deemed suitable for cell culture.

Figure 1. Set-up used in the production of ice-microspheres.

Preparation of bacterial cellulose/PDLLA composite scaffolds via thermally induced phase separation

A total of three different samples were prepared in order to investigate the structure of microbial cellulose/PDLLA. These samples consist of 5 wt.%, 30 wt.% and 47 wt.% of bacterial cellulose, respectively. Firstly, PDLLA was dissolved in DMC at a concentration of 5% (w/v). Different amounts of bacterial cellulose were then dispersed in the polymer solutions and subsequently frozen in liquid nitrogen (-196°C) from the bottom of the samples. This was to ensure that the temperature gradient was uni-axial. Porous structure was obtained by removing the solvent through sublimation.

Preparation of bacterial cellulose/PDLLA composite scaffolds via thermally induced phase separation using ice microspheres as an *in situ* porosifier

The melt point of DMC (ca. $2-4^{\circ}\text{C}$) makes it unsuitable for use in combined TIPS/ice-microsphere processing. Therefore, chloroform was selected as the solvent due to its lower melting point (ca. -64°C). In addition to this, chloroform is also highly

immiscible with water and this will cause the hydrophilic bacterial cellulose to preferentially migrate onto the ice-microspheres. A total of 0.83 g of PDLLA was added to 16.6 ml of chloroform and the resulting solution was added into a tube containing 0.36 g of dry microbial cellulose. Once this sample has been prepared, 4.7 g of ice microspheres was then added into this tube and placed in a freezer at -25 °C to ensure that chloroform stayed in the liquid phase and the ice microspheres stayed in the solid phase. This was to make sure that the microbial cellulose has time to re-orientate itself to the interface. The mixture was then frozen in liquid nitrogen and freeze-dried at -196 °C.

Characterisation of the scaffolds

The porosity and the density of the scaffold were characterised using pycnometry (GeoPyc 1360, Micromeritics, Dunstable, UK) in conjunction with helium pycnometry (AccuPyc 1330, Micromeritics, Dunstable, UK). In order to evaluate the morphology of the samples, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was conducted using a JSM-5300 SEM (JEOL, Welwyn Garden City, UK). The samples were fixed onto SEM stubs using carbon tabs and sputter coated with gold. Fourier Transformation Infrared Spectroscopy was obtained using a Perkin Elmer (Beaconsfield UK) FTIR operated in attenuated reflectance mode. Spectra were obtained from 800 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structure of the scaffolds without ice-microspheres

Figure 2 shows the scanning electron micrographs of neat PDLLA, 5 wt.% microbial cellulose/PDLLA, 30 wt.% microbial cellulose/PDLLA and 47 wt.% microbial cellulose/PDLLA, respectively. It can be seen that micro-tubular pores, typical of the TIPS process [19,20] existed in the structure. This was due to the fact that the temperature gradient was uni-axial (from bottom going upwards). When the temperature gradient was maintained uni-axially during thermally induced phase separation, parallel microtubes can be formed [23].

From Figure 2, it can also be seen that the structure changes from an organised structure to a more disordered structure as the concentration of microbial cellulose increases. Such observation proved that the microbial cellulose was indeed preventing the polymer structure from collapsing during phase separation. Due to the high microbial cellulose concentration, the polymer was able to retain its random structure in the liquid phase when it solidified. When the microbial concentration in the mixture decreased, the mixture does not have enough cellulose to prevent the polymer structure from shrinking and hence, the structure was denser. This explains the structural difference between 0 wt.%, 5 wt.%, 30 wt.% and 47 wt.% microbial cellulose concentrations at constant freezing temperature.

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrographs of (a) Neat PDLLA (b) 5 wt% microbial cellulose/PDLLA (c) 30 wt% microbial cellulose/PDLLA (d) 47 wt% microbial cellulose/PDLLA

Structure of the scaffolds with ice-microspheres

Figure 3. Scanning electron micrographs of scaffolds produced with 30 wt.% microbial cellulose. Picture on the left: at low magnification, right: at high magnification

Figure 3 shows the structure of 30 wt.% microbial cellulose in PDLA, prepared in the presence of ice microspheres. It can be seen that the ice microspheres had a significant structural impact on the samples as the structure looked very different from all the previous samples. The spherical-like structure was induced by the ice microspheres. Microbial cellulose is very hydrophilic; in a mixture of microbial cellulose, solvent (chloroform) and ice microspheres, the microbial cellulose migrates to the surface of the ice-microspheres to reduce hydrophobic interactions. When the migration to the surface of the ice microspheres is completed and the sample was freeze dried, resulting in the structure shown in Figure 3.

This structure also represents the phase equilibrium prior to freeze drying where the ice-microspheres, the solvent (chloroform) and the microbial cellulose co-existed in the mixture. Since no phase separation was observed during the preparation of this sample, it can be further inferred that PDLA actually migrated along with the microbial cellulose to the surface of the ice microspheres. This implied that the bonds between the microbial cellulose and PDLA were very strong. Such observation also supports the theory of microbial cellulose prevented the shrinking or the collapsing of the polymer structure. It was established earlier that the microbial cellulose will prevent the polymer structure from shrinking or collapsing during phase transition. This could only be possible if the bonds between the polymer and the microbial cellulose were strong enough, which was proven in this experiment. Therefore, it can be concluded that it was the bonds established between the microbial cellulose and the polymer which prevented the polymer structure from shrinking during phase transition.

In addition, this sample also contained highly interconnected pores. This was made possible by the use of ice microspheres. In order to minimise the hydrophobic interactions, the microbial cellulose will migrate together with PDLA onto the surface of the ice microspheres. Therefore, these ice microspheres will become the template for microbial cellulose and PDLA to build on. The ice microspheres will cause the cellulose to stretch (instead of just one plain layer, a web-like spherical structure can be formed) such that all the microbial cellulose can maximise the hydrophilic interactions. This event will lead to a highly porous and interconnected structure shown in the figures. It is also worth mentioning that the all the spherical-like structure was larger than 100 μm but smaller than 500 μm . This was due to the fact that the ice microspheres were between 100 μm and 500 μm in diameter. Although the pore size distribution is fairly broad, it can further be refined by using a finer mesh during the ice microspheres preparation.

Fourier Transformation Infrared Spectra

FTIR spectra (shown in Figure 4) clearly show the presence of hydroxyl groups in the composites. The hydroxyl groups, which are present on the surface of the bacterial cellulose, impart a more hydrophilic character to the composite scaffolds. The characteristic wavenumbers for both PDLA at 1750 cm^{-1} and microbial cellulose at 3350 cm^{-1} can be observed in Figure 4. In addition to this, it can also be seen that as the microbial cellulose concentration increased, the polymer concentration decreased (using Beer-Lambert Law). This was because the more microbial cellulose present in the scaffold, the less polymer content there will be. It can also be inferred that the addition

of microbial cellulose to the polymer does not alter the polymer chemistry. Such results can be obtained from the fact that there were no peak shifts or the occurrence of new peaks in the spectroscopy. This implied that the microbial cellulose does not react with the polymer and formed a new compound. It will only attach itself onto the surface of the polymer structure, providing mechanical strength and rigidity to the scaffold to a certain extent, which is a highly desirable situation.

Figure 4. ATR-FTIR spectra of the prepared samples

Porosity and density of the scaffolds

The porosity dictates the volume where the stem cells can grow in the scaffold and the density gives an indication about the mass per unit volume of the scaffolds. Table 1 shows the porosity and the density of these scaffolds.

Table 1. Porosity and density measurements of the scaffolds

Sample	Porosity [%]	Density [g cm^{-3}]
Neat PDLLA	93.8	1.23 g cm^{-3}
30 wt.% BC/PDLLA	98.2	1.50 g cm^{-3}
47 wt.% BC/PDLLA	93.1	1.50 g cm^{-3}
30 wt.% BC/PDLLA produced using ice-microspheres	92.6	1.37 g cm^{-3}

It can be seen that the density of the scaffold increased as the microbial cellulose concentration increased. This was due to the fact that more mass was present in the scaffold for the same amount of volume. Therefore, the density of the scaffold was expected to increase as a function of microbial cellulose concentration. On the other hand, the porosity of the scaffold decreased as a function of microbial cellulose

concentration. The porosity of the ice-microsphere templated scaffolds is suitable for future use in growing haematopoietic stem cells.

CONCLUSIONS

A highly porous and interconnected scaffold structure can be produced by introducing microbial cellulose into PDLLA. The more the microbial cellulose concentration in the scaffold, the more porous the structure became and this is beneficial for the growth of haematopoietic stem cells. The introduction of ice-microspheres into the structure created an interconnected scaffold of controlled pore size, with pores lined by cellulose nano-fibrils, which mimic the collagen fibrils. These scaffolds exhibit improved wettability over PLA due to the presence of more hydroxyl groups. The scaffolds possessed suitable mechanical integrity to withstand handling and conditions in cell culture. Such scaffolds are promising candidates for the 3D culture of haematopoietic stem cells.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

JJB acknowledges the experimental assistance of Aulfah Azman and the EPSRC for funding. This work was supported by the Challenging Engineering Programme (EP/E007538/1) of the UK Engineering Physical Science Research Council (EPSRC).

References

1. L. K. Nielsen. *Annu. Rev. Biomed. Eng.* **1**, 129-152.
2. C. Smith, *Cancer Control*, 2003, **10**, 9-16.
3. A. Mantalaris, N. Panoskaltsis, J. H. D. Wu, *Encyclopedia of Biomaterials and Biomedical Engineering*, Marcel Dekker Inc., 2004, 1508-1517.
4. C. Y. J. Ma, R. Kumar, X. Y. Xu, A. Mantalaris, *Biochemical Engineering journal*, 2007, **35**, 1-11.
5. (a) T. M. Dexter, T. D. Allen, L. G. Lajtha, R. Scofield, B. I. Lord, *J. Cell. Physiol.*, 1973, **82**, 461-472; (b) T. M. Dexter, T. D. Allen, L. G. Lajtha, *J. Cell. Physiol.*, 1977, **91**, 335-344.
6. C. M. Agrawal, R. B. Ray, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.*, 2001, **55**, 141-150.
7. J. Bagley, M. Rosenzweig, D. F. Marks, M. Pykett, *Exp. Hematol.*, 1999, **27**, 496-504.
8. N. Banu, M. Rosenzweig, H. Kim, J. Bagley, M. Pykett, *Cytokine*, 2001, **13**, 349-358.
9. Y. Li, T. Ma, D. A. Kniss, S. T. Yang, L. C. Lasky, *J. Hematother. Stem Cell Res.*, 2001, **10**, 355-368.
10. C. M. Agrawal, R. B. Ray, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.*, 2001, **55**, 141-150.
11. T. Tun, H. Miyoshi, T. Aung, S. Takahashi, R. Shimizu, T. Kuroha, M. Yamamoto, N. Ohshima, *Artif. Organs*, 2002, **26**, 333-339.

12. W. K. Czaja, D. J. Yound, M. Kawecki, R. M. Brown, *Biomacromolecules*, 2007, **8**, 1-12.
13. H. Bäckdahl, M. Esguerra, D. Delbro, B. Risberg, P. Gatenholm, *Journal of Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine*, 2008, **2**, 320-330.
14. W. Czaja, A. Krystynowicz, S. Bielecki, R. M. Brown, *Biomaterials*, 2006, **27**, 145-151.
15. G. Helenius, H. Bäckdahl, A. Bodin, U. Nannmark, P. Gatenholm, B. Risberg. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.*, 2006, **76A**, 431-438.
16. S. Yamanaka, E. Ono, K. Watanabe, M. Kusakabe, Y. Suzuki, *European Patent No.* 0396344, 1990.
17. Y C Hsieh, H Yano, M Nogi, S J Eichhorn, *Cellulose 2008* **15**, pg 507 – 513.
18. Y. S. Dong, C. Guo, P. H. Lin, L. H. Yin, Y. P. Pu, *Key Engineering Materials*, **288-289**, 381-384.
19. K. Rezwan, Q. Z. Chen, J. J. Blaker, A. R. Boccaccini, *Biomaterials*, **27**, 3413-3431.
20. J. J. Blaker, J. C. Knowles, R. Day, *Acta Biomaterialia*, 2008, **4**, 264-272.
21. O. van den Berg, J. R. Capadona, C. Weber, *Biomacromolecules*, **8**, 1353-1357.
22. M. Roman and W. T. Winter, *Biomacromolecules*, **5**, 1671-1677.
23. P X Ma, R Zhang, *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research* **56**, 469 – 477.